

Self Help Groups and Bank Linkage Programmes: A Study of India and Andhra Pradesh

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Abstract

The SHG Bank Linkage programme distinctly differs from other micro-finance programmes across the world mainly in terms of its greater emphasis on savings. The basic philosophy of saving first and credit next is assumed to be one of the strengths of the programme. The programme rests on the premise that members will develop the habit of thrift so that during post-SHG phase they can avail of loan. This, besides increasing their self-reliance in meeting the credit needs of the group members will also help in efficient deployment of credit among the members as their own money is at stake. The existing savings and lending products mainly from institutional sources were not adaptable to the rural poor. Keeping this in view, the programme has shifted the entire responsibility of innovating the saving and lending products to SHGs with a broader framework. In this paper an attempt is made to analyze the SHG-bank linkage programme in India as well as Andhra Pradesh.

Key Words: SHGs, Bank Linkage, Community Investment Fund, Revolving Fund

Introduction

Access to adequate and timely credit at affordable rates is critical for the rural poor to alleviate high-cost debt and invest in livelihood opportunities. Despite the Government of India's (GOI's) best efforts, financial inclusion of the rural poor has been beset with multiple challenges. Lack of adequate banking infrastructure and human resources in rural areas, unplanned expansion leading to unviable bank branches and low levels of financial literacy amongst the rural populace have been some of the key challenges. The most vulnerable communities, who often had no formal credit history or ability to provide collateral, have often been the worst affected. Inability to access loans from banks meant that the poorest had to resort to moneylenders for loans at usurious rates of interest that invariably led them into a toxic debt trap. In this context, the SHG-Bank Linkage programme that synthesizes 'formal

financial systems'(in terms of a formal institution providing credit) with the 'informal sector'(comprising of rural poor with no formal credit history - exclusively women in case of DAY-NRLM), has emerged as a preferred vehicle for providing financial services to the hitherto unbanked poor.

The pilot project was conceived of as a partnership between SHGs, Banks and NGOs in which the Reserve Bank of India (RBI) allowed banks to lend directly to SHGs and NABARD committed to providing re-finance and promotional support. The studies subsequently conducted by NABARD to assess the impact of the linkage project indicated significant reduction in the transaction costs for both banks and borrowers, besides a gradual increase in the income level of the SHG members. These findings led to the formalization of the SBLP in 1995.

Intervention

Since the design of DAY-NRLM made major departures from the existing poverty reduction programmes, the Government of India sought to establish a "proof of concept" in high poverty areas before scaling it to all States and Union Territories. In this context, the GOI sought credit from the International Development Association (IDA) to implement the National Rural Livelihood Project (NRLP), under DAY-NRLM. Between July 2011 and June 2018, the NRLP helped set up implementation systems, demonstrated social mobilization/ capacity building and provided initial capitalization and facilitated credit linkage of community institutions across the country with the formal banking sector, largely the Public Sector Banks. By the end of the project, NRLP had mobilized more than 7.5 million rural poor women into 650,000 Self Help Groups, 41000 Village Organizations and nearly 2500 Cluster Level federations. DAY-NRLM has been able to mobilize over 60 million women into over 6 million SHGs. The SHGs have successfully leveraged approximately INR 2,870 billion (USD 41 billion) as loans from banks since 2013-14. NRLM has been able to achieve these results by leveraging the experiences of states such as Andhra Pradesh (AP), Telangana, Tamil Nadu (TN) and Bihar in promoting SHG-Bank Linkage and instituting critical demand and supply side interventions.

Generating Resources in Perpetuity

DAY-NRLM has made a departure from the erstwhile Swarnajayanti Gram Swarozgar Yojana (SGSY) by abolishing the concept of capital subsidy to both groups and individuals. Instead, DAY-NRLM provides capitalization support to institutions of the poor (SHGs and CLFs) as grants, which are then passed on to the SHG member as loans to be

repaid with interest by the members. This on-lending-repayment-on-lending cycle ultimately leads to an increase in the corpus of these institutions, creating “resources in perpetuity” for the village community. This strengthens their institutional and financial management capacity, creating a culture of timely repayments and help build a track record to attract mainstream bank finance. These grants include a Revolving Fund (RF) of up to INR 15,000 per SHG as corpus that serves the members’ credit needs as well as acts as catalytic capital to leverage repeat bank finance. The project also provides a Community Investment Fund (CIF) of up to INR 25,000 per SHG at the Cluster Level Federation (CLF) to meet the credit needs of the members through SHGs and Village Organizations (VOs), Since the design of DAY-NRLM made major departures from the existing poverty reduction programs, the Government of India sought to establish a “proof of concept” in high poverty areas before scaling it to all States and Union Territories. In this context, the GOI sought credit from the International Development Association (IDA) to implement the National Rural Livelihood Project (NRLP), under DAY-NRLM. Between July 2011 and June 2018, the NRLP helped set up implementation systems, demonstrated social mobilization/ capacity building and provided initial capitalization and facilitated credit linkage of community institutions across the country with the formal banking sector, largely the Public Sector Banks. By the end of the project, NRLP had mobilized more than 7.5 million rural poor women into 650,000 Self Help Groups, 41000 Village Organizations and nearly 2500 Cluster Level federations. DAY-NRLM has been able to mobilize over 60 million women into over 6 million SHGs. The SHGs have successfully leveraged approximately INR 2,870 billion (USD 41 billion) as loans from banks since 2013-14. NRLM has been able to achieve these results by leveraging the experiences of states such as Andhra Pradesh (AP), Telangana, Tamil Nadu (TN) and Bihar in promoting SHG-Bank Linkage and instituting critical demand and supply side interventions. Some of these strategies are mentioned below. Intervention and to serve as working capital for collective activities at various levels. Cumulatively, the community institutions under DAY-NRLM have been provided about INR 102 billion as capitalization support (approx. USD 1.5 billion). The Reserve Bank of India issues annual “master circulars” that lays down the ground rules for the Banks to extend credit to the women SHGs under DAY-NRLM. The extant Master Circular, requires the banks to extend credit of at least Rs.1,00,000 (~1400USD) or 6-8 times their corpus amount to SHGs as their first bank-linkage. This amount is increased for subsequent linkages.

Simplification of procedures and application formats

The sheer number of banks involved in lending to SHGs meant that there were enormous variations in application procedures and forms for opening a savings account or a loan account. DAYNRLM consistently engaged with the Reserve Bank of India (RBI), Indian Banks Association (IBA), NABARD and scheduled commercial banks to resolve these discrepancies. This led to the RBI issuing a detailed master circular with specific directions on procedures, loan eligibility and terms for credit to SHGs by banks, and the IBA standardizing the saving bank account and loan application forms across banks.

Supporting banks in conducting their business

Leveraging the experience of states like Andhra Pradesh and Bihar, DAYNRLM has placed a trained Community Resource Person (CRP), called Bank Mitra, within bank branches to facilitate non-cash transactions such as filling application forms, following up on repayments etc. This strategy helps in reducing the workload on the bank branch officials and inspires confidence in SHG members who are unfamiliar with the formal banking system. As of March 2020, about 21,000 Bank Sakhis support SHGs to engage with their lending partners while also ensuring that the bank portfolio remains healthy.

Sources of Funds

Self Help Groups have access to multiple sources of funds. The SHGs need to be guided and prepared to access the Mission funds they are entitled to. More significantly, the SHGs need to be guided to accessing bank credit and other financial services on a continuous basis.

Gradual Augmentation of Member Savings

The savings rate (savings per member per meeting/per month) should be enhanced, taking into account the saving potential of the members; and introduction of new saving products like optional/ voluntary savings apart from regular savings. Savings may also be targeted for specific purposes and emerging needs of members such as education of children, construction of houses and for meeting health emergencies. Regular internal lending and recovery will contribute to higher income from interest charges. If the SHGs undertake regular internal lending and recovery of loans, the interest income would exceed the total member savings in about 8 years.

Review of Literature

Archana Sharma and Anil Kumar Srivastava (2017) made an attempt to study the status of Micro-Finance and Self-Help-Groups (SHGs) in India. According to authors the overall development of a country depends on the development of the poorer section of the

society and due to the high levels of poverty and unemployment in developing countries, the overall development can never be achieved. For this development, Government of India has launched a programme known as SHG-Bank Linkage Programme. The study found that in the last few years, it was noticed that SHG-BLP had lost its focus and has been overshadowed by the MFI sector in the country. While the growth of MFI sector has been remarkable, the SHG Bank Linkage Program has also been growing steadily despite its slow growth in priority states, concerns regarding book keeping, quality of groups and diminishing attention of banks.

Prachi Bhansali (2019) in his research paper examines the growth of the SHG-bank linkage programme in India. The author makes a comparative study – region-wise based on the three major variables – savings, credit disbursed and loan outstanding by the SHGs which are further classified as total savings of SHG, average savings per SHG, total credit received by SHG, average credit received per SHG, total loan outstanding and loan outstanding per SHG. The study found that the SBL programme was on an increase every year and then reach out to the Southern region was significantly very high and that of the North-Eastern region was very low. It was also found that there is an impact of savings per SHG on the credit received per SHG and there is an impact of savings on the loan outstanding per SHG as well but there is no significant impact of average credit received per SHG on average loan outstanding per SHG.

Rashmi Rekha Pradhan and D. P. Misra (2020) in their study examined the SHG-Bank linkage position and report the trend and position of such innovative scheme for poverty mitigation of the SHGs members. The study reveals that maximum members have joined the SHG for poverty eradication and generating extra income for the family. The study observes that there is a significant rise in the income level of the SHG members. The study also reveals that there is significant change in the socio-economic conditions of SHG members. The study also discloses that maximum respondents are satisfied with SHGs performance particularly with regard to SHG Bank linkage for financial inclusion. The study concludes with few important suggestions for better functioning of SHG-Bank linkage scheme for financial inclusion and the socio-economic development of the SHG members.

Muthu N., (2021) in his research paper an attempt has been made to analyse the progress of SHG-Bank linkage programme in India during the period between 2007-2008 and 2019-2020. The study shows that there is significant raise in the amount of savings of SHGs with banking sector and amount of loans disbursed to SHGs, During this study period.

However, the agency-wise analyses of savings of SHGs and loans disbursed to SHGs show that the Commercial banks lead in getting savings of SHGs and loans disbursed to them followed by Regional Rural Banks and Co-operative banks. Notwithstanding the remarkable progress, geographically there has been skewed development of SHG-Bank linkage programme in India. There is wide regional disparity in the spread of SHGs, savings of SHGs with banks and loans disbursed to SHGs under this programme. The outreach of this programme is spectacular in Southern region while North, West and Eastern regions are lagging behind. In view of the large outreach, predominant position and the possible benefits to the poor, it is very important to see the benefits of this programme to reach across all sections of the society and regions. So far, the SHG movement in India is mostly South-Centric and it is yet to take off the real sense in other regions of India.

Haldhar Sharma et.al. (2022) in their study analyses the loan disbursement of SHG for the last two decades. In the study, it was observed that the number of SHGs with commercial and regional rural banks are increasing. In contrast, SHGs affiliated with cooperative banks are declining. The loan disbursement amount increases for SHGs related to commercial and regional rural banks while it declines for cooperative banks. The analysis revealed that the numbers of SHGs are growing in Madhya Pradesh, and the loan disbursement amount is also increasing significantly over the study period. The authors conclude that the SHGs has instilled a sense of synergy among its members, allowing them to progress up the socio-economic ladders from passive observers to active partners/stakeholders in the development process. In India, SHGs have evolved into a possible weapon for women's empowerment, social solidarity, and socio-economic improvement of the disadvantaged in their communities.

Sripal Srivastava et.al. (2024) in their study pointed out that SHG bank linkage programme has its impact on sustainable development. It has been found to directly and indirectly impact the attainment of many UN sustainable development goals. The study analyzes the effectiveness of microfinancing programmes in rural India in achieving UN sustainable development goals. The study recommended that more quantitative and qualitative research be conducted to assess the performance of SHG-BLP in achieving SDGs in rural areas. The authors concludes that research must be focused not only on the shorter-term impacts like reduction in poverty, gender equality, reduced inequalities and eradication of hunger; instead, there has to be an assessment of the performance of SHG-BLP for longer-

term impacts like the development of industry and infrastructure and promotion of peace and justice in the area.

Results and Analysis

NABARD has pioneered the concept and implemented the SHG Bank Linkage programme since 1992 for providing easy access of institutional credit to rural poor. Since one decade of the programme implementation has elapsed, there is an imperative need for putting in place a system of evaluating the impact of the programme and provide continuous feedback on the magnitude of benefits accruing to the people. Table 1 Gives the clear picture of the SHG-Bank linkage programme in India during 2013-14 to 2022-23.

Table 1
Financial Year Wise SHG-Bank Linkage Status in India

S. No.	Financial Year	Total SHG	Growth Rate	Total Amount (in crores)	Growth Rate
1	2013-14	1009443	-	22944.16	-
2	2014-15	1159341	14.85	23953.19	4.40
3	2015-16	1286451	10.96	30440.03	27.08
4	2016-17	1622445	26.12	42586.46	39.90
5	2017-18	2752936	69.68	44256.09	3.92
6	2018-19	3144221	14.21	61456.97	38.87
7	2019-20	3420794	8.80	70921.74	15.40
8	2020-21	4777030	39.65	84622.63	19.32
9	2021-22	4289231	-10.21	120365.83	42.24
10	2022-23	5133867	19.69	156690.47	30.18
Total		28595759		658237.57	

Source: DAY-NRLM

The data in table 1 shows that the number of Self-Help Groups linked to banks in India are gradually increasing except in 2021-22. During 10 years of study the number of SHGs linked to banks increased more than 5 times. In 2013-14 the SHGs financed by banks stood at 1009443 and the same increased to 5133867 by 2022-23. It is pertinent to note that the total amount of loan extended to SHGs is gradually showing upward trends during all 10 years of study. The Growth rate of SHGs financed by banks varies between 8.80 per cent (2019-20) to 69.68 per cent (2017-18). But negative growth rate of -10.21 per cent, in number

of SHGs financed by banks is registered in (2021-22). On the other hand, the growth rate with regard to total loan amount ranges between 3.92 per cent (2017-18) to 42.24 per cent (2021-22). the average amount per SHG varies between Rs. 1, 60, 670 (2017-18) to Rs. 3.05, 209 (2022-23).

SHG-Bank Linkage in Andhra Pradesh

Table 1 Gives the clear picture of the SHG-Bank linkage programme in India during 2013-14 to 2022-23.

Table 2

Year Wise SHG-Bank Linkage Status in Andhra Pradesh

S. No.	Financial Year	Total SHG	Growth Rate	Total Amount (in crores)	Growth Rate
1	2013-14	300019	-	9016.87	-
2	2014-15	189019	-37.00	5990.5	-33.56
3	2015-16	304202	60.94	10308.39	72.08
4	2016-17	340377	11.89	12872.24	24.87
5	2017-18	606359	78.14	13131.86	2.02
6	2018-19	627280	3.45	18245.03	38.94
7	2019-20	692857	10.45	20395.88	11.79
8	2020-21	998371	44.09	25648.73	25.75
9	2021-22	739334	-25.95	39388.42	53.57
10	2022-23	776736	5.06	45316.09	15.05
	Total	5574554		200314	

Source: DAY-NRLM

It can be noted from table 2 that the total number SHGs linked to banks in Andhra Pradesh State is gradually increasing except in 2014-15 and 2021-22. Highest number of SHGs (998371) in the state were linked to banks in 2020-21. On the other hand, least number i.e. 189019 of SHGs were linked to banks in 2014-15. The loan amount extended to the SHGs is gradually showing upward trends from 2014-15 onwards. During the same period the amount of loan extended to SHGs in the state increased more than 7.5 times. With regard to total SHGs benefited under bank linkage scheme positive growth rate is registered in 8 out of 10 years of the study. On the other hand, with regard to loan amount extended to SHGs

positive growth rate was registered 9 out of 10 years of study. The average loan amount per SHG varies between Rs.2, 16, 569/-(2017-18) to Rs. 5, 83, 416/- (2022-23).

Conclusion

Women's social liberation elevates their stature in society. It increases family respect, boosts self-esteem, prevents gender bias, and decreases dowry deaths. It encourages women to be leaders and raises the family's income. Promotion of women's empowerment develops the next generation of women and addresses the issue of future unemployment. And women who have achieved empowerment despite obstacles and struggles are a contented and self-assured group in society who serve as role models for other women.

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